

Speculation on Maxwell's Demon and Hidden Work

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Maxwell's demon, proposed by Maxwell in 1867, suggests that given an ideal gas of volume V next to an empty volume V , a demon could select particles with an energy $e > e_1$ and allow them to pass to the empty volume (but not back). Then, entropy would decrease and according to (1) there would be "seemingly... no work". This would violate the second law of thermodynamics.

We consider a thought example of a one dimensional gas and argue that an elastic hit of a particle with energy e against the wall requires an amount of work $-e$ to stop it (thus gaining knowledge of e) and then another $-e$ to send it back with e in the opposite direction. This $-2e$ of work is balanced by $2e$ of work by the wall on the other side. We next consider a tiny window along the wall (next to the empty V) which opens only for the first particle with energy e_1 , allowing it into the empty V . It then remains shut, but a tiny window slightly above along the y axis does the same. This way each particle with e_1 can only enter the empty V , but cannot escape back into the first container.

We show that for $e_1 > 3/2 RT$, entropy is guaranteed to decrease, but argue that there is an imbalance of work. The particle with e_1 reaching the window is associated with work $= -2e_1$ from the other side of the wall. An amount of work e is done to stop it (hence ascertaining its energy), but then instead of sending it back with e , the window opens allowing it into the empty V with some energy $-e_2$. Then: $-2e_1 - e_2 + e_1 = \text{work} \neq 0$. In other words, there is a loss in entropy, but work is done so the second law of thermodynamics is not violated in this example.

Maxwell's Demon

Maxwell's demon was presented by Maxwell in 1867. An ideal gas sits in a volume V to the right of an empty container of volume V . As particles approach the wall, adjacent the empty container, the demon ascertains their energy and only allows ones with energy $e > e_0$ into the empty container. This leads to a loss in entropy, but "seemingly... no work" is done (1). We try to consider an example in which there is hidden work.

Ideal Gas

We consider a one-dimensional ideal gas of length L to the right of an empty container of length L . We suggest that when a gas particle of energy e (all have the same rest mass) hits the right wall, an amount of work $-e$ is done to stop the particle (hence gaining knowledge of its e value) and then another amount $-e$ is performed to send it back in the opposite direction with the same energy. Thus, the right wall does $-2e$ amount of work, but this is balanced by $2e$ done by the left wall. Thus, overall the work is zero as expected.

We next consider a tiny window in the wall adjacent to the empty L container. When a particle hits the window, work $-e$ is done to stop the particle ($e = \text{kinetic energy}$) hence the particle's e is known. If $e = e_1$, then the window opens and the particle is sent to the left with energy e_2 . Hence, such a particle is associated with:

Work: $-2e_1$ from right wall + $-e_2+e_1$ from window ((1))

All other particles are sent back to the left with the same energy. Thus, the e_1 particles are associated with an imbalance in work by the walls, or in other words, work is done. This scenario, which appears to be a Maxwell's demon case, can then not be said to represent a decrease in entropy with no work being done.

As soon as one particle with e_1 is let through a window, this window remains shut and a tiny window just above on the y axis performs the same role. This way, e_1 particles may enter the empty L box, but cannot return to the full L box. The particles e_1 are now classical moving with a constant speed and bounce back and forth in the once empty container.

We next consider entropy changes using the Sackur-Tetrode equation:

$$S/N = \ln(V/N \{ b E/N \}^{\text{power } 3/2}) + 5/2 \quad ((2)) \quad b \text{ is a constant}$$

We first argue that the particles with energy e_1 originally have entropy because they are part of the ideal gas, but then have no entropy (except the same volume entropy) when they enter the empty container as they are completely deterministic and simply bounce back and forth elastically

Assume originally that one has N_0 particles with energy $E_0 = 3/2 NRT$
 Assume that: N_1 , e_1 particles move into the empty L container. Then,

$$S_f/N_f = \ln\{ V / \{N_0-N_1\} [(E_0 - N_1e_1)/ (N_0-N_1)]^{\text{power } 3/2} \} + 5/2 + 3/2 \ln(b) \quad ((3))$$

If one assumes that: $N_1/N_0 \ll 1$ and $N_1e_1/E_0 \ll 1$, then the change in the number in $\{ \}$ is:

$$N_1/N_0 (5/2 - e_1/ (1.5 RT)) \quad ((4))$$

If e_1 is a high energy particle, i.e. $e_1 > 1.5 RT$, then ((4)) is a negative number which reduces the original number in $\{ \}$. This leads to a guaranteed loss of entropy which augments the loss of entropy of the particles e_1 . $e_1 > 1.5 RT$ then represents a Maxwell demon case, but as noted, work is done so the second law of thermodynamics is not violated.

If $e_1 < 1.5RT$, then the number in $\{ \}$ increases meaning that the entropy per particle left in the left container increases, but the entropy of the N_1 , e_1 particles has decreased and so in this case, one has to be more careful to ascertain whether the entropy decreases overall. Nevertheless, the first case, $e_1 > 1.5RT$ satisfies the entropy decrease, but is associated with work being done by the left wall/window.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to present a one dimensional ideal gas scenario with a window which opens to one particle with energy e_1 , allowing it to move into an empty container of the same size to the left. The window remains shut and a new window opens just above for an e_1 particle. This way, e_1 particles in the left container cannot return to the right. These e_1 particles lose their entropy and we show that if $e_1 > 1.5 RT$, then entropy per particle for all particles left in the ideal gas decreases. At first glance, this has the appearance of a Maxwell demon example and breaks the second law of thermodynamics. We argue, however, that for each particle with energy e in an ideal gas, $-2e$ amount of work is done by the right wall. The first $-e$ ascertains the value of e and another $-e$ is added, sending the particle back into the gas. Normally, $2e$ is then done by the left wall.

For the window and e_1 particles, only e_1 work is done by the window at first. After that, the particle is sent into the next box with energy e_2 and work $-e_2$ is done. Thus, the overall work by walls for the e_1 particle is: $-2e_1 - e_2 + e_1$ which is nonzero. Thus, entropy decreases overall if $e_1 < 1.5 RT$, but work is done and so the second law of thermodynamics is not violated, we argue.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Maxwell%27s_demon
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sackur%E2%80%93Tetrode_equation